

Bhutanese Elementary Teachers' Assessment Conceptions

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to investigate Bhutanese elementary teachers' conceptions about assessments to determine teachers' inclination towards improving conceptions (formative) or accountability conceptions (summative). Assessment conceptions were measured using the abridged version of CoA-III Abridged (CoA-III A) inventory proposed by Brown (2006) which includes four pre-determined assessment conceptions: assessment for improvement, assessment for student accountability, assessment for school accountability, and assessment as an irrelevance. The data was collected from 111 elementary teachers using an online survey questionnaire. Findings indicate that teachers conceive that the purpose of assessments is for improvement. They also conceived of assessments as irrelevant. There was a strong positive correlation between the conception of assessments for improvement and student accountability and a positive association between improvement and irrelevance conceptions. It was concluded that teachers have positive conceptions about assessment, but they often experience an assessment practice dilemma between the improvement and accountability purposes of assessment.

Keywords: Assessment conceptions, sub-conceptions, improvement, accountability, irrelevance, formative, summative assessment.

Introduction

The education system of Bhutan experienced a significant transition in the educational assessment structure. The shift from traditional written examinations to continuous formative assessments (CFA) for grades PP-3 is one of the notable transformations in the assessment system. Specifically, written examinations for grades PP-3 have been removed since 2020, fully adopting CFA in all subjects taught in these grades. The transformation was aimed to better assess student competencies and provide effective feedback aligning to the Bhutan Education Blueprint 2014-2024 and the National Education Policy (Ministry of Education, 2014, 2019). Teachers' conceptions significantly impact their instruction and practices, including their implementation of policy shifts such as the changes to assessment practices. Thus, the transformation in the assessment system raises concerns about teachers' competencies and conceptions about assessments particularly when there is scant training in formative assessment techniques and a heavy reliance on traditional examinations.

The crucial role that teachers' conceptions about assessment play in shaping their professional practices such as informing instructional activities are discussed in the literature. According to Black and Wiliam (2009), assessment guides teachers' instructional decisions. Brown (2008) and Barnes et al. (2015) argue that teachers' conceptions about assessment considerably influence how they involve students in assessment activities and respond to assessment systems. Understanding these conceptions is imperative for policy makers and educational leaders, for it impacts the implementation of new curricula and assessment systems.

Remesal (2007) underlines the importance of understanding teachers' conceptions about assessments as they are key to success of educational reforms. In Bhutan, where quality assessment is emphasized, it is fundamental to explore these conceptions to inform educators and policy makers effectively. Therefore, this study investigates Bhutanese elementary teachers' conceptions about assessments using Brown's Four Constructs of assessment (2006), intending to determine whether teachers lean towards improvement or accountability-oriented conceptions. The findings could inform policymakers and educators in understanding the likely impact of the recent shift towards CFA and the removal of written examinations from grades PP to 3.

Literature Review

Assessment Conceptions

A wide range of studies on teachers' conceptions about assessment is evident in the literature. According to Thompson (1992), conceptions are the lenses people use in making sense of people, events and interactions wherein the meaning of conceptions is connected to mental constructs shaped by environment and culture. Brown has conducted a series of studies to investigate and capture the conceptions about assessment that teachers possess. Brown (2004, 2006) identifies four purposes of assessment: to improve teaching and

learning, to hold students accountable, to hold teachers and schools accountable and assessment is irrelevant. Brown (2004, 2006) includes the conception that assessment is irrelevant to education arguing that assessment is irrelevant to teachers' life and work and students as well because assessments could be bad, easily ignored, or inaccurate.

Brown, through the series of studies, developed and modified a four-factor tool called Conception of Assessment (CoA-III) with 50 items (Brown, 2004) and Conception of Assessment Abridged version (CoA-III A) with 27 items (Brown, 2006) to capture teachers' beliefs about assessment. The items of CoA-III Abridged is included in the methodology section below. This survey tool was subsequently validated in several contexts such as in New Zealand and Australia (Brown, 2006, 2008), Hong Kong (Brown et al., 2009), Egypt (Gebril & Brown, 2014), China (Brown & Gao, 2015), and India (Brown et al., 2015).

Studies by Brown (2008) and Brown et al. (2009) demonstrate that the New Zealand and Queensland primary teachers and teachers in Hong Kong largely believe assessments are for improving teaching and learning and increasing student accountability. There was a strong positive correlation ($r=.91$) displayed by Hong Kong teachers between the conception of improvement and that of student accountability (p. 354), likely influenced by its culture of examination in education. The findings suggest that Hong Kong teachers understood improvement and accountability to be inseparable. Likewise, Chinese teachers also noted a strong relationship between assessment for improvement and student accountability. These findings suggest that Bhutanese teachers might hold the same views, as Bhutan's education also emphasizes high stake examinations for significant academic transition and accreditation. Further, Brown and Gao (2015) investigated the assessment conceptions of Chinese teachers, highlighting a dichotomy where teachers believe the purpose of assessment is for both development and accountability, ranging from growth of individual to control by institutions.

Additionally, Remesal (2011) conducted a study to explore practising teachers' conceptions of the functions of assessment in basic education in Spain. The study focused on four dimensions of assessment: the learning process, the teaching process, accreditation of learning, and teachers' professional accountability (Remesal, 2011). It established a two-pole continuum with pedagogical and societal functions at either end, placing the four dimensions of assessment in between. Further, Remesal (2011) articulated the four dimensions into pure and mixed conceptions on the continuum, claiming that these dimensions are not distinct and that together they form a conception and so can hardly be separated. Remesal (2011) discovered that assessment has two dimensions: pedagogical (improving learning and teaching) and societal (accountability).

An investigation on empirical research on pre-service and in-service teachers' conceptions about assessment by Barnes et al. (2015) organised the conceptions reported in previous studies on a continuum of purposes, from pedagogical conceptions to accounting conceptions. It presented three findings on teachers' conceptions about assessment. First, as claimed by Brown and Harris (2009), belief systems about assessment

formed by teachers are shaped by the legal frameworks and sociocultural priorities of their societies. Second, the review noted that some studies have made a distinction between knowledge of assessment and beliefs about assessment in their research into assessment conception. The review, therefore, cautions that asking teachers about the conceptions about assessments may reflect their knowledge rather than their conceptions. Consequently, it appears that differentiating teachers' assessment knowledge and conceptions may indicate distinct explanations of assessment practices. Third, Barnes et al. (2015) conclude that assessment can either enhance learning or be used to punish and control students, teachers, and schools. Thus, the study identifies two purposes of assessment: improvement and accountability.

In contrast, Postareff et al. (2012) provided a different perspective by analysing pharmacy teachers' conceptions about assessments. They proposed a continuum from reproductive to transformational conceptions. Reproductive conceptions focus on repeating correct information (aligning with accountability), and transformational conceptions stress deep understanding and critical thinking (aligning with improvement). The study found that most pharmacy teachers held reproductive conceptions, reflecting the emphasis on factual knowledge necessary in their field. Therefore, this finding suggests that teachers may hold assessment conceptions about assessments based on levels of institutions (school, college or university) and the subjects they teach.

Formative and Summative Assessments

According to Black and Wiliam (1998, 2009, 2018), integrating formative and summative assessment functions is crucial for effective assessment practices. Formative assessment supports learning by offering feedback that teachers and students can use to evaluate their own progress and that of their peers, with the aim of adjusting teaching and learning activities accordingly (Black & Wilson, 2009). Summative assessment offers a final overview of student abilities and knowledge. The assessment conceptions highlighted in all the literature that are reviewed here capture these functions.

In Bhutanese education system, there have been several reforms made to blend the formative and summative assessments towards quality education. As such, there are two types of assessments from grade 4 to 12 called continuous assessments, which are understood as formative assessments, and summative assessments. The continuous assessments are practised using arrays of assessment tools such as portfolios, checklists, anecdotal records, quizzes, debates, presentations, and gallery walks. These continuous assessment practices are eventually reflected in numerals in a student's report card. Summative assessments include midterm examinations and annual examinations. Thus, the report card of a student reflects the numeral scores of both continuous assessments and summative assessments at the end of an academic year.

On the other hand, the assessment practice in lower elementary grades (PP to 3) is called as continuous formative assessment (CFA). This practice was introduced in the year 2020 by completely removing written examinations (summative assessment) for these grades. According to the Royal Education Council (2019),

under the CFA there are a wide variety of assessment tools suggested in teacher manuals that attempt to capture all learning domains including cognitive, psychomotor, and affective. Therefore, this major shift of abolishing summative assessment and fully embracing formative assessment raises concerns about teachers' competencies, readiness and assessment conceptions.

In conclusion, while the primary purposes of assessment are mostly seen for improvement (formative) and accountability (summative), the conceptions about assessment held by teachers can vary due to contextual influence, culture, and policy leading to an array of overlapping conceptions. Thus, this research captured the assessment conceptions of Bhutanese elementary teachers within the framework of Brown's (2006; 2008) CoA- IIIA to determine if these conceptions align with the new shift in assessment system.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to investigate Bhutanese elementary teachers' conceptions about assessments using the four constructs proposed by Brown (2004, 2006) to determine the teachers' inclination towards improving conceptions or accountability conceptions. The investigation will help Bhutanese school leaders and policy makers support the successful implementation of recent assessment reforms which involve replacing examinations from grade PP-3 introduced in elementary classes to CFAs. This study is guided by the following aims and objectives:

1. Investigate the current conceptions about assessments held by elementary teachers in Bhutan using the Conception of Assessment (CoA-III A) Inventory developed by Brown (2006).
2. Analyze how teachers' assessment conceptions are affected by their gender, teaching experience, teacher education level, grade taught, subject taught, and assessment education/training received.

Thus, the research questions of the study are guided by these aims and objectives:

1. What are Bhutanese elementary teachers' conceptions about the purpose of assessment?
2. In what ways do teachers' gender, teacher education level, years of teaching experience, grade taught, subject taught and assessment education/training determine teachers' conceptions about assessments?

Methodology

Ethical Consideration, Population and Sampling

The author of this study sought and received approval from the Department of School Education under the Ministry of Education in Bhutan. Subsequently, the proposal for this study was reviewed by the Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) of the University of Adelaide and provided with the approval number H-2020-121. Following these, the principals of 25 sample schools obtained from the list provided by the Ministry of Education, were sent emails seeking written approval and distribution of the online survey questionnaire to the potential respondents in their schools. The web-based survey program, Survey Monkey was chosen to develop and send the questionnaire. The respondents were provided with Participation Information Sheets to

allow them to make informed choices about their participation in the survey. In light of slow response due to COVID-19, the online survey inclusive of Participation Information Sheets was also shared on Facebook by forming a closed group where only the invited members (potential teacher participants) could access the page. The identity of the respondents was immediately eliminated upon the submission of the survey and all data were stored with password protection, in the data set of the University of Adelaide R: drive and University of Adelaide Box according to Data management. Any form of personal identity was not revealed in the final report. Thus, the confidentiality and anonymity were well protected.

The target population of this quantitative online survey study was elementary teachers working in public schools in Bhutan who teach any subject from grade PP – 6. The sample was inclusive of general teachers and Dzongkha language teachers. The general teachers are trained to teach subjects taught in elementary classes except for Dzongkha (national language) which is taught by Dzongkha language teacher. Hence, the study in collecting sample did not consider other demographic features of the participants except that they taught elementary grades.

The study employed cluster sampling of the schools, meaning, sampling was conducted involving more than one stage. In a cluster sampling design, the researcher ascertains the organization or groups (Creswell, 2014). Initially, a list of schools obtained from the Ministry of Education helped to identify 577 schools with elementary grades. From this group, 25 schools were selected through convenience sampling. In convenience sampling, the sample is chosen based on availability and convenience for respondents (Creswell, 2014, p.158). However, in this study convenience sampling was conducted not for respondents but for sample schools. The convenience sampling for the school was done considering the factors such as access to Internet, availability of known individual to the researcher for contact and representing the researcher and the location of the school, reflecting practical difficulties during COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. The schools were closed and teachers worked from home when sampling, consents, and data were collected through second and third quarter of 2020. Although convenience sampling is a less desirable sampling method (Creswell, 2014), it is known for its low cost, lower time commitment, and ease of survey administration, which encourages greater participation and may generalise the result to parallel subjects (McMillan & Schumacher, 2006).

Instrument: Conception of Assessment Abridged version (CoA-III A)

The abridged (27 items) CoA-III A was used to investigate teachers' conceptions about assessments upon receiving permission from G.T.L Brown. None of the items in the instrument were edited or changed from the original CoA-III A. However, the items were measured using a slightly different scale from that of Brown (2002; 2006). The scale included a 5-point scale, 1-strongly disagree, 2-disagree, 3-neutral, 4-agree, 5-strongly agree, similar to Calveric (2010) and Rosas (2014) who had also used the same tool in their studies. In the studies done by Calveric (2010) and Rosas (2014) on teachers' assessment conceptions, both the authors

used 5-point scale with original items proposed by Brown. This 5 point scale was used for familiarity and ease of comprehension. The survey items of CoA-III A are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

CoA-III A with 27 Items

Conception of Assessment
1. Assessment provides information on how well schools are doing.
2. Assessment places students into categories.
3. Assessment is a way to determine how much students have learned from teaching.
4. Assessment provides feedback to students about their performance.
5. Assessment is integrated with teaching practice
6. Assessment results are trustworthy.
7. Assessment forces teachers to teach in a way that is contradictory to their conceptions.
8. Teachers conduct assessments but make little use of the results.
9. Assessment results should be treated cautiously because of measurement error.
10. Assessment is an accurate indicator of a school's quality.
11. Assessment is assigning a grade or level to student work.
12. Assessment establishes what students have learned.
13. Assessment informs students of their learning needs.
14. Assessment information modifies ongoing teaching of students.
15. Assessment results are consistent.
16. Assessment is unfair to students.
17. Assessment results are filed and ignored.
18. Teachers should take into account the error and imprecision in all assessment.
19. Assessment is a good way to evaluate a school.
20. Assessment determines if students meet qualifications.
21. Assessment measures students' higher order thinking skills.
22. Assessment helps students improve their learning.
23. Assessment allows different students to get different instruction.
24. Assessment results can be depended on.
25. Assessment interferes with teaching.
26. Assessment has little impact on teaching.
27. Assessment is an imprecise process.

Additionally, demographic items including gender, years of teaching experience, highest teacher qualification, grades taught, subject taught, and assessment education/training received were added to the survey questionnaire. The demographic items were included to test their significant differences, if any, on teachers' conceptions about assessment.

Data Collection

There were two platforms created to collect data from the respondents: a weblink to Survey Monkey distributed to school principals (formal), and a closed Facebook page group (informal). The Facebook page was created to increase the response rate, in light to slow and low turnover of initial respondents due to the closure of schools during COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. The responses were automatically stored in Survey Monkey in the researcher's account. When the survey was closed both formally and informally, there were 59

responses submitted through the web link and 53 responses submitted through the Facebook page who also used the Survey Monkey. Upon validating the data, 1 respondent completed the demographic items but left the CoA-IIIA items blank. Thus, the respondent was removed from the Excel sheet and not included for further analysis which made the total respondents to 111.

Data Analysis

The data were analysed using a quantitative data analysing software *Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 26)* and *Analysis of Moment Structure (AMOS; AMOS graphic version 23)* (Arbuckle, 2014). AMOS is an IBM SPSS segment designed for the analysis of covariance structure models such as structural equation modelling (SEM), path analysis, and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) (Barnidge & De Zuniga, 2017, p.1). Descriptive data statistical techniques were used to analyze the results for the descriptive data by computing frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation. Prior to the analyses of results according to the research questions, the demographic information data were run through descriptive analysis to obtain an overview of respondents' characteristics. Further, structural level analysis, (CFA using AMOS) was conducted to evaluate the construct validity of the data with assessment conception and to choose the best CFA model that fitted the data. The CFA also depicted the inter-correlation between the four conceptions of assessment. Also, scale reliability was tested for internal consistency by calculating Cronbach's alpha at 0.7. Following the CFA, the conceptions of assessment of elementary teachers were determined by computing frequency, composite mean scores and standard deviation using the corresponding data. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to test the significant difference that the independent variables from demographic information had on teachers' conceptions of assessment.

Results

Descriptive Result of Demographic Data

The demographic data is summarized in Table 2. A total of n=111 respondents returned the survey of which 72.1% (F=80) were female and 27.9% (M=31) were male indicating more female participants. The teacher qualification was classified into four categories: Primary Teaching Certificate (PTC), Bachelor's in Education (B Ed), Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE), and Master's Degree. From the total respondents, 18.9% (21) had PTC qualification, 59.5% (66) had B Ed qualification, 8.1% (9) had PGDE, and 13.5% (15) had a master's degree. A majority of the respondents held a bachelor's degree in education. The number of years in teaching was categorised as 0-5 years, 6-10 years, 11-15 years, and more than 15 years. As shown, 27.0% (30) respondents had teaching experience between 0-5 years, 6.3% (7) respondents had teaching experience between 6-10 years, 27.0% (30) respondents had teaching experience between 11-15 years and 39.6% (44) respondents had teaching experience of above 15 years. This result indicated that more senior

teachers were teaching in elementary classes than the recent teachers. In grades taught, 14.7% (16) respondents taught in Pre-Primary, 12.8% (14) respondents taught in Grade 1, 10.1% (11) respondents taught in Grade 2, 11.9% (13) respondents taught in Grade 3, 11.0% (12) respondents taught in Grade 4, 13.8% (15) respondents taught in Grade 5 and the highest percent of 25.7% (28) respondents taught in Grade 6. In subjects taught, 10.8% (12) of the respondents taught Dzongkha, 46.8% (52) taught English, 25.2% (28) taught Mathematics, 9.9% (11) taught Science and 7.2% (8) taught Social Studies. The results portrayed that more respondents were teaching English during the survey.

Table 2

Demographic Data

Variable	Number of Respondents (N)	Percent %
<i>Gender</i>		
Female	80	72.1
Male	31	27.9
<i>Highest Teacher Qualification</i>		
Primary Teacher Certificate (PTC)	21	18.9
Bachelor's in education (B ed)	66	59.5
Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE)	9	8.1
Master's Degree	15	13.5
<i>Years of Teaching Experience</i>		
0-5 years	30	27
6-10 years	7	6.3
11-15 years	30	27
More than 15 years	44	39.6
<i>Grade Taught</i>		
Pre-Primary (PP)	16	14.7
Grade 1	14	12.8
Grade 2	11	10.1
Grade 3	13	11.9
Grade 4	12	11
Grade 5	15	13.8
Grade 6	28	25.7
<i>Subject Taught</i>		
Dzongkha	12	10.8
English	52	46.8
Mathematics	28	25.2
Science	11	9.9
Social Studies	8	7.2
<i>Assessment education/training</i>		
None	2	1.8
Undergraduate Assessment Course	2	1.8
Graduate Assessment Course	28	25.2
Post Graduate Assessment Course	13	11.7
Professional Development conducted by School	24	21.6
Professional Development conducted by MOE or RE	42	37.8

Construct Validity of Conception of Assessment (CoA-III A): A Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Model fit indices were examined to test the data fit by running a Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA). CFA is a statistical technique to test if a set of observed variables represents a specified number of underlying latent constructs as hypothesised by the researcher (Bentler, 2007). It tests how well the data fit a predefined model where specific paths between variables are theoretically determined, and all other paths are set to Zero (Klen, 2000). It consists of expected relationships that are allowed to vary, and non-expected relationships are controlled to zero, ensuring only the hypothesized paths are assessed for their strengths and validity (Byrne, 2001). The measures such as Chi-Square (χ^2), degrees of Freedom (df), Chi-Square Minimum/degrees of Freedom (CMN/df), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) were chosen to test the model fit.

The model fit indices were compared among four CFA alternative models of One Factor Model, Orthogonal Four Factor Model, Correlated Four factor Model, and Hierarchical model. As shown in Table 3, the indices χ^2 , df, CMN/df, TLI, CFI, and RMSEA (Schreiber et al., 2006) improved significantly with the subsequent models from the one-factor model through the hierarchical model. Since the Correlated Four Model had the best indices comparatively, it was accepted for further analysis. Confirmatory Factor Analysis was conducted with AMOS (Arbuckle, 2005) and the model had acceptable fit characteristics (Table 3: $\chi^2=347.475$; $df=224$; $\chi^2/df= 1.551$; $CFI=0.776$; $TLI=0.724$; $RMSEA=0.05$.)

Table 3

TCoA-III Model Fit Indices for Bhutanese Elementary Teachers

N0	Model	Chi-Square	df	CMN/df	TLI	CFI	RMSEA
1	1-factor mode	600.067	324	1.852	.479	.553	.062
2	Orthogonal model	573.237	324	1.769	.529	.597	.059
3	<i>Correlated model</i>	<i>347.475</i>	<i>224</i>	<i>1.551</i>	<i>.724</i>	<i>.776</i>	<i>.050</i>
4	Hierarchical model	351.277	226	1.554	.723	.773	.050

Assessment Conceptions of Bhutanese Elementary Teachers as Captured by CoA-III A.

Figures 1 and 2 present the results of the path analysis of the Correlated Four Factor model with standardised and unstandardised estimates and R^2 values. The four unobserved variables in the models were conceptions about assessment for improvement (Imprv), assessment for student accountability (StdAc), assessment for school accountability (SchAc), and assessment as an irrelevance (Irrlv) with 23 items after the evaluation of factor loadings and squared correlation measuring assessment conceptions. Initially there were

27 items and 3 items having factor loading less than 0.3 were eliminated in each CFA run, retaining the 23 items having factor loadings more than 0.3. The unobserved variable of assessment for improvement (Imprv) had 11 items loaded on it, assessment for student accountability (StdAc) had 3 items, assessment for school accountability (SchAc) had 3 items, and assessment as an irrelevance (Irrlv) had 6 items loaded. Further, each unobserved variable was correlated with each other. It may be noted that the curved lines with double-headed arrows represent correlations and the straight lines with one arrow represent regression paths from latent factors to predicted items.

Figure 1

Bhutanese Elementary Teacher Responses to CoA-III A; Standardised

Figure 2

Bhutanese Elementary Teacher Responses to CoA-III; Unstandardised

Correlation Among the Four Constructs of Assessment Conceptions

The correlated four-factor model presented that the four constructs of assessment conceptions were correlated. The correlations between the four constructs of assessment conceptions are presented in Table 4. The results showed that conceptions about assessment for improvement and assessment for student accountability had a high positive correlation ($r=.71$; $p<0.01$). A positive moderate correlation was noted between conceptions about assessment for student accountability and assessment for school accountability ($r=.66$; $p<0.01$). Likewise, conceptions about assessment for improvement and assessment for school accountability also had a moderate positive correlation ($r=.61$; $p<0.01$). Interestingly, conceptions about assessment as irrelevant were weakly but positively correlated to conceptions about assessment for improvement ($r=.15$; $p<0.05$). Similarly, a positive association existed between conceptions about assessments as irrelevant and assessments for student accountability ($r=.37$; $p<0.05$). However, correlation between conceptions about assessments as irrelevant and assessments for school accountability is insignificant ($r=.06$; $p>0.01/0.05$).

Table 4*Correlation Between the Four Constructs of Assessment Conceptions*

	Irrelevance	Improvement	School Accountability	Student Accountability
Assessment as an irrelevance	1			
Assessment for Improvement	.147*	1		
Assessment for school accountability	.057	.606**	1	
Assessment for student accountability	.368*	.716**	.656**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Result Analysis and Discussion

Assessment Conceptions of Bhutanese Elementary Teachers

A descriptive statistical analysis was conducted to obtain frequency (n), Mean (M), and Standard Deviation (SD). Table 5 highlights the frequency (n), Means (M), and Standard Deviation (SD) of the four conceptions about assessments. The mean score ranged from (M=4.13) the highest to (M=3.03) the lowest. The mean scores between 1 to 1.7 denoted strongly disagree, 1.8 to 2.5 denoted disagree, 2.6 to 3.3 denoted neutral, 3.4 to 4.1 denoted agree and 4.2 to 5 denoted strongly agree. The belief that assessments are for improvement scored the highest mean (M=4.13) with (SD=.40) suggesting that Bhutanese elementary teachers agree with the conception that assessments have an improvement purpose. It mirrors the findings of Brown (2008) with New Zealand and Queensland teachers, and Clevair (2010) with teachers in central Virginia in the United States. Primary school teachers in New Zealand and Queensland, as well as Grade 3 through Grade 5 teachers in central Virginia, agreed more with the conception that the purpose of assessment is for improvement (Clevair, 2010).

Meanwhile, the conception that assessments are for student accountability had a mean score of M=3.85 with SD=.50 and assessments for school accountability scored relatively the same mean scores of (M= 3.72 with SD=.70) (Table 5). These scores suggested that most participants hold the conception that assessments have accountability purposes for both students and schools. In contrast, the New Zealand and Queensland teachers agreed that assessments hold purposes for student accountability but not for school accountability (Brown, 2006, 2008, 2011). In Clevair's (2010) study, the teachers held a neutral view about school accountability too. The mean score of (M=3.03; SD=.72) depicted that the teachers held neutral views about

assessments as irrelevant unlike the teachers in Queensland, New Zealand and Hongkong (Brown, 2008; Brown et al 2009) who disagreed with this conception.

Table 5

Descriptive Statistics for Assessment Conceptions

Constructs	n	M	SD
Assessment for improvement	102	4.13	.40
Assessment for student accountability	102	3.85	.57
Assessment for school accountability	102	3.72	.70
Assessment as an irrelevance	102	3.03	.72

The results of the relationships between the four conceptions showed that they were positively correlated. There was a statistically significant positive association of teachers' conceptions about assessment for improvement and assessment for student accountability ($r=.72$; $p=0.01$), indicating that Bhutanese teachers conceive that student learning is aligned with student accountability. A similar and strong positive correlation was observed with Hong Kong teachers ($r=.91$) (Brown et al., 2009), and Chinese teachers ($r=.80$) (Brown et al., 2011); as well as with New Zealand and Queensland teachers, though with only a weak positive correlation (Brown, 2004; 2008). This comparison shows Bhutanese elementary teachers' conception that the purpose of assessments is for holding students accountable and to improve students' learning. Thus, Bhutanese elementary teachers' conception of the purpose of assessment for improving and accountability go hand in hand. Bhutanese students receive their entry in tertiary education based on their performance in Grade 12 and Grade 10 (high stake examinations) which might have shaped teachers' conceptions of assessment that showed a strong positive correlation between using assessments for improvement and assessments for student accountability.

The two accountability conceptions related to schools and students also had a positive moderate correlation ($r=.66$), similar to the observation made with New Zealand and Queensland teachers (Brown, 2004, 2008). This implies that teachers see a strong connection between assessments being used for student and school accountability. This conception might be tied to the reality in Bhutan where teachers and schools are evaluated based on students' overall examination results. This result implies that most teachers hold the conception that if an assessment can be used to improve student accountability, this also provides a basis for schools to be evaluated. A moderate positive correlation between improvement and school accountability ($r=.61$) suggests that Bhutanese teachers conceive that assessment is about improvement of teaching and learning, it is also about the improvement of school and showing the accountability of school. A similar finding was observed in Brown's (2004, 2008) study of New Zealand and Queensland teachers, and Clevar's (2010) study of teachers in central Virginia.

Similarly, the conception that assessments are irrelevant was positively correlated to the conception that assessments should be used for student accountability ($r=.37$). This finding matched the findings from New Zealand's primary teachers (Brown, 2004, 2008) that assessing students by examining and grading is irrelevant. On the other hand, Bhutanese teachers expressed a conception that making students accountable through gradings and examinations also means persuading them to improve their learning. Surprisingly, unlike any of the past studies, this study found that assessment for improvement was positively related to assessment as an irrelevance ($r=.15$) although statistically insignificant ($P>0.01/0.05$). This finding suggests that Bhutanese elementary teachers do not view these two conceptions as opposites. This association illustrates that while Bhutanese elementary teachers conceive that assessments are for improvement of teaching and learning, they also conceive that assessments might be irrelevant. Finally, the conception that assessments are irrelevant had almost no relation with school accountability ($r=.05$). This finding mirrored the finding with New Zealand teachers, which rejected the international notion that assessment for school accountability is not healthy for quality schooling (Brown, 2008). One of the significant concerns that emerged in this study is the positive relation of irrelevance with three remaining conceptions (improvement, student, and school accountability), which means teachers conceive that assessment is irrelevant and interferes with teaching and learning but also conceive assessments cannot be denied as they bring improvement.

Overall, the structure of Bhutanese elementary teachers' assessment conceptions appears conflicting and complex. A high moderate correlation between assessment for improvement and assessment for accountability (student and school), and a low but positive correlation between assessment for improvement and assessment as an irrelevance suggest that Bhutanese elementary teachers conceive of assessments for improvement, but as teachers and schools are evaluated based on students' end of year academic results, the teachers tend to hold the conception that assessments are irrelevant if an assessment must be used for improvement rather than for accountability.

Demographic Information and Assessment Conceptions; Differences Across Groups

While examining statistically significant differences caused by independent variables on dependent variables, a few demographic characteristics had significant differences on one or the other sub- conception of assessment but not on the conceptions of assessment as a whole. The independent variables are the factors that might influence the outcome or dependent variable of the study. The independent variables included gender, highest teacher qualification, years of teaching experience, grade taught, subject taught, and types of education or training received on assessment education. There was no significant difference between gender (females and males), grade taught, and intensity of assessment education/training received on any of the assessment conceptions. Nonetheless, years of teaching experience, level of teacher education and subject taught had statistically significant differences ($p<0.05$) in one or the other assessment conception among the four

conceptions. Table 6 draws the descriptive and post hoc analysis of independent variables which had statistically significant differences on one or the other assessment conceptions.

Table 6

Results of Significant Difference in Assessment Conceptions by Demographic Information (Post-hoc tests (Bonferroni)

Independent variable	Dependent variable	Comparison	Mean Difference	S.E	P-level at <0.05
No. of Years in teaching	Assessment for school accountability	11-15 years vs > 15 years	.475* (M=4.00- M=3.52)	.170	.039
		PTC vs Masters	.566* (M=3.94- M=3.38)	.195	.032
Teacher qualification	Assessment for student accountability	B Ed vs Masters	.537* (M=3.91- M=3.38)	.164	.009
		Dzongkha vs social studies	.820* (M=3.36- M=2.54)	.347	.054
Subject taught	assessment as an irrelevance				

The years of teaching experience had significant differences only on the sub conception that assessment is for school accountability. The post hoc analysis in Table 6 showed that the significant difference was between years of teaching experience with 11-15 years and with more than 15 years, MD=.475, SE=.17, p=0.039. The mean score for teachers teaching between 11-15 years was M=4.00; SD=2.87 and for teachers teaching more than 15 years was M=3.52; SD=2.82. The difference indicated that the number of years in teaching of the respondents may influence their conceptions about assessment.

The level of teacher education had statistically significant difference only on a sub-conception that assessment is for student accountability where the post hoc analysis presented that the difference was between PTC and master's teachers, MD=.556, SE=.195, p=.032, and between PGDE and master's teachers, MD=-.537, SE=.164, p=.009. The mean scores for PTC teachers were M=3.94, for Master's degree teachers M=3.38 and for B Ed M=3.91. The difference shows that teacher qualification level could affect their conceptions about assessment. Given the higher means scored by PTC education level (M=3.94) teachers with lower qualifications tend to conceive more that assessment is for student accountability. Cleavair (2010) had noted a similar trend, where teachers who did not attain degrees beyond the bachelor's level conceived that assessment is for student accountability.

The subject taught by the teachers had a statistically significant difference in assessment as an irrelevance and the post hoc analysis showed that the significant difference was between Dzongkha and Social Studies teachers, MD=.969, SE= .347, p=.54. The mean scores for Dzongkha and Social Studies were M= 3.36

and $M=2.54$ respectively. Dzongkhag teachers more often than Social Studies teachers conceived that assessments are irrelevant. It may be interpreted that Dzongkha is comparatively a new developing subject; it does not yet have enough assessment tools and techniques. It is also likely that Dzongkha teachers are not given equivalent teacher education compared to other teachers due to a lack of resources written in Dzongkha. Therefore, subjects taught are likely to bring variations in the conceptions about assessment as portrayed by the significant difference.

In this study, it was expected that types or intensity of assessment education/training received by teachers would have a significant influence on their conceptions of assessment. Nearly all public-school teachers in Bhutan undergo teacher education training for two years (PTC-which does not exist now), for four years (B. Ed) or for 1 year (PGDE), where they are taught the principles of assessment and evaluation. Furthermore, need-based workshops are conducted for teachers whenever new reforms are introduced. Nonetheless, only those teachers whose roles match with the purpose of workshops are required to attend needs-based workshops. When the written examination was abolished and CFA was fully adopted, more than 200 elementary teachers were given training on the implementation of CFA in January 2020 who further provided training to the remaining elementary teachers (Dolkar, 2020). Therefore, it was anticipated that assessment education/training would have a significant impact on assessment conceptions. The non-significant difference of assessment education/training received on assessment conceptions may indicate that such education and training have failed to address, or influence teachers' conceptions about assessment.

Overall, the results of demographic characteristics and assessment conceptions confirmed the findings of Brown (2008), that none of the teachers' demographic characteristics had a significant influence on the conceptions of assessment but on some sub-conceptions of assessment held by New Zealand teachers. Therefore, the demographic characteristics of teachers seemed to be irrelevant in determining how strongly a teacher agreed with each conception about assessment.

Conclusion

As teachers in this study agree more with the conception that assessment is for improvement, they require knowledge of a range of assessment tools to effectively implement formative assessments in the classroom. Like preceding studies by Black and Wiliam (1998) and Brown (2008), the prominence attached to an array of assessment practices emphasised that teachers need to use a variety of assessment tools and methods, both informal and formal, aimed at improvements. Therefore, teachers need to be provided with high-quality assessment methods and tools that facilitate improvement. The high positive association between assessment for improvement and assessment for student accountability suggests that teachers have strong conceptions on examinations in bringing learning improvements among learners. Similarly, the moderate positive association between assessment for improvement and assessment for school accountability indicates that Bhutanese teachers view assessments as tools not only for improving teaching and learning but also for

advancing school development and demonstrating school accountability. Further, the positive association between assessment for improvement and assessment as an irrelevance is a concern for policymakers. Given the positive conceptions about assessments held by Bhutanese elementary teachers, the prospective teachers must be trained effectively, and in-service teachers are given relevant capacity-building opportunities. Therefore, teachers must be provided with enough time, resources, and professional support by school administration to help them realise their positive conceptions about assessment.

It is acknowledged that the study was limited by a small sample which may not have truly represented the whole population of elementary teachers in Bhutan. Therefore, generalizability of the results may have been affected. The magnitude of seriousness and commitment of teacher participants to complete the self-reported questionnaire on assessment conceptions provides cautionary and limited interpretations.

Future research on assessment conceptions may be extended to middle and higher secondary teachers in the country. Teachers' assessment practices and students learning achievement may be included as additional variables. Studies on students' conceptions about assessment could be useful to teachers and curriculum developers.

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